

From Data to Score: Prospects for AI in African Fintech (Rwanda, Kenya, Nigeria)

An Ethical Data Initiative Report
Technical University of Munich

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1. Introduction: AI for Financial Technology

A quiet revolution is underway in Africa's financial sector, driven not by politics but by the rapid integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into financial technology (Fintech). This transformation is particularly evident in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda, where AI is reshaping how individuals and businesses access, manage, and conceptualize money. Nigeria and Kenya stand as market leaders; Kenya's M-Pesa is a global benchmark for mobile money, while Nigeria's Fintech sector has attracted the majority of the \$1.4 billion invested in African Fintech in 2022 (Moodley et al., 2024; Baldini, 2024). Although smaller, Rwanda is strategically positioning itself as a regional AI hub (FintechNews Africa, 2024), aiming to significantly expand its Fintech sector within the next four years (Republic of Rwanda & Access to Finance Rwanda, 2024, 24; Rwanda Center for the Fourth Industrial Revolution (C4IR), 2025). More generally, Fintech has experienced significant growth across the African continent over the last few years, driven by improved network coverage and surging mobile penetration (Moodley et al., 2024; Mothobi & Kebotsamang, 2024).

The integration of AI into African Fintech is poised to address a fundamental challenge: the continent's large unbanked and underbanked population. A prominent AI application gaining traction is AI-driven "alternative credit scoring" (ACS) (Avickson & Ogunola, 2024, 6129). These new scoring models promise to extend access to credit by leveraging non-traditional, "alternative" data, such as mobile phone usage and digital transaction histories, and machine learning algorithms to assess creditworthiness more efficiently and inclusively than conventional scoring systems allow (Nuka & Ogunola, 2024, 1053). This approach is touted as particularly beneficial for "unbanked and underbanked" communities, who have often been excluded from formal financial services due to a lack of credit history (Ngwenya, 2024, 2).

However, the rapid adoption of AI in this space raises critical questions about its risks. While most existing literature emphasizes Fintech's potential to increase financial inclusion and drive economic growth, far less attention has been given to how Fintech may introduce or deepen risks such as discrimination, data privacy violations,

cybersecurity vulnerabilities, and external dependence on non-African platforms. Especially overlooked is the context of specific African countries like Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda. This report seeks to fill this critical gap by examining the extent to which the development of AI-driven Fintech systems in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda can be carried out in ethical, inclusive, and secure ways. While AI is promoted for its potential to drive financial inclusion, there remains a notable need for a critical analysis of the systemic inequalities and risks it may introduce or reinforce.

Addressing these challenges, likely to surface in Rwanda's context, will be essential to the success of its Fintech ambitions (Munyegera, 2024, 38). With public trust in digital lending still limited (Access to Finance Rwanda, 2024, 47), and only 32% of adults considered financially literate (Republic of Rwanda & Access to Finance Rwanda, 2024, 11), many users may be ill-equipped to navigate or contest automated decisions. Meanwhile, regulatory frameworks are still catching up, leaving individuals exposed to opaque and potentially unfair lending practices (Brailovskaya et al., 2022, 30; Seohyun, 2024, 28). In this context, transparency is not just a guiding principle but a necessary foundation for building trust, shaping effective regulation, and ensuring that digital credit systems serve rather than exclude vulnerable populations (Adeoye et al., 2024, 294).

The report draws on academic literature, policy documents, and market data to explore the observable practices of AI-driven ACS in African lending technology (Lendtech) companies, their ethical implications, as well as broader risk dimensions of fairness, privacy, cybersecurity, and outside control. After an overview of our methods, the first substantive section (Section 3), analyses Lendtech practices by focusing on two critical stages of the scoring process: the collection and structuring of data, and the algorithmic transformation of that data into credit decisions. The report approaches these processes from a data science perspective, treating credit scoring as a structured "data journey" (Leonelli 2020; Beaulieu & Leonelli, 2022). This conceptual lens provides a practical framework for examining how decisions are encoded, where ethical concerns emerge, and what levers exist for oversight and intervention. By tracing what can be observed in this often opaque landscape, the report aims to support a clearer, more accountable, and ultimately more inclusive approach to digital lending.

A further section focused on risks (Section 4) identifies exclusion and discriminatory bias as recurring themes across a range of risk dimensions and highlights the role of infrastructures, data literacy, and outside influence in amplifying harm. Further, it introduces exploitation as an underlying systemic concern and emphasizes that Fintech's inclusionary promise cannot be fulfilled without active risk mitigation and socially embedded design.

Finally, Section 5 examines challenges centred on AI use in Fintech that are distinct to Rwanda's unique regulatory, infrastructural, and cultural landscape, and relates them to distinct opportunities to support fairness, responsibility, and participation. The strategic interventions discussed range from regulatory reforms to innovative, user-centered technology solutions.

This research intends to help policymakers, entrepreneurs, and development actors create a Fintech future for Rwanda that benefits all citizens. It does this by linking technological innovation with principles of data ethics and inclusive governance. While Fintech is largely viewed as a driver of financial inclusion, there remains a need for critical analysis of the risks and systemic inequalities it may reinforce. By offering reflections for emerging Fintech hubs like Rwanda, the report argues that Fintech is not a neutral tool but must be treated a collective responsibility.

2. Methods

This report was developed by graduate students and professors with interdisciplinary backgrounds in philosophy, history, social studies of science, management, and computer science, in partnership with the Center for Law and Innovation at the Certa Foundation, Rwanda. It emerged from a "data clinic" run by the Chair for Philosophy and History of Science and Technology and the Ethical Data Initiative (EDI) at the Technical University of Munich (TUM).

Data clinics are an interactive problem-solving and teaching format developed by the EDI and designed to bridge theory and practice in data governance and ethics, with the

overarching goal of promoting active ethical reflection at every stage of data work (Ethical Data Initiative, 2025). Guided by EDI researchers, students work collaboratively in groups on a challenge posed by a partner organisation; in this case, on ethical issues linked to the use of AI in Fintech across Africa, but especially as related to the Rwandan context—the challenge posed by the Certa Foundation. This report is the synthesis of the three student groups' analysis and proposals.

While the authors do not have personal ties to Kenya, Nigeria, or Rwanda, the three main countries examined, our understanding has been shaped by our firm commitment to gender equality and global justice. This positionality inevitably informs our research choices, especially in how we interpret risks and fairness in Fintech. The report is moreover grounded in the philosophy, history, and social studies of science and technology, which attend, among other factors, to the ways technological development is inherently shaped by power dynamics.

Given the limited availability of peer-reviewed, context-specific studies on Fintech in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda, and its risks, our research also draws upon so-called grey literature, industry reports, and internet sources, such as market overviews focused on relevant Fintech providers in digital lending and credit, as well as mobile money and payments. While every effort was made to ensure credibility, some sources may not conform to traditional academic standards. Other sources for this research include Fintech rankings, company websites and app privacy policies, and investment data from platforms like Crunchbase. Due to the relative opacity and inconsistency of the resources at hand, the report synthesizes the available information to the best of our knowledge.

Topics and concerns were identified and discussed because of their rich potential for debate in academic and policy environments and their specific relevance to Fintech. While issues of transparency and accountability are acknowledged, they are not discussed as standalone categories. These challenges and opportunities are closely interlinked, and a clear separation is neither always possible nor desirable. Some arguments apply broadly to Fintech, while others pertain more narrowly to AI-enabled or

alternative lending services. This report also includes limited overviews of the regulatory landscape as concerns Fintech-specific policy, AI governance, and data protection regulation. Our aim is not legal analysis, however, and we refrain from evaluating the broader legislative or regulatory environment, as well as the effectiveness or enforcement of these regulations due to limitations in our legal expertise.

3. Data Management Challenges: The Case of Alternative Credit Scores

3.1. Mapping the Journey from Data to Score

ACS refer to systems that assess creditworthiness using non-traditional data sources, such as mobile phone metadata, utility payment histories, or social media activity, instead of relying exclusively on formal financial records (Adeoye et al., 2024, 293; The World Bank Group, 2024, 23). These systems have gained particular prominence in emerging economies, where large segments of the population remain excluded from traditional credit infrastructures. In these contexts, the proliferation of mobile phones and digital services has produced vast quantities of data, frequently categorized as “alternative”, which are increasingly leveraged for financial profiling purposes by Lendtech companies (Rizzi et al., 2021). The use of such data is intended to expand financial inclusion by providing credit access to those without conventional credit histories. However, as discussed further in Section 1.3, the processes of collecting, processing, cleaning, and analysing alternative data raise significant ethical concerns, especially regarding transparency, fairness, and data privacy (Rizzi et al., 2021).

To manage the scale and complexity of alternative data, machine learning algorithms are employed. These tools enable rapid decision-making and allow for the processing of large volumes of both structured and unstructured data—capabilities that exceed the limits of conventional credit scoring techniques (Nuka & Ogunola, 2024, 1053, 1055). However, the use of these systems introduces new forms of opacity, with limited explainability emerging as a key concern. When transparency is not prioritized, users

are left unable to understand or contest decisions that directly impact their financial opportunities (Umeaduma & Adedapo, 2025, 6649). Importantly, algorithmic outputs are shaped by a range of design decisions made by system developers and institutions, which influence both the process and its outcomes. These dimensions will be discussed further below.

It is crucial to recognize that ACS systems are not only opaque because of the algorithms themselves; opacity is also produced through the broader institutional and infrastructural arrangements in which these systems are embedded.

From the user's vantage point, however, these complexities remain largely invisible. Many digital lending platforms prominently advertise instant credit decisions. For instance, the Kenyan company Tala promises applicants they can "get an instant decision and receive funds directly" (Tala, n.d.-a), reinforcing the perception that loan approval is wholly automated. The exemplary user experience—a submission of personal data via a mobile application, followed by near-immediate feedback—suggests a streamlined, mechanized process.

This perception, however, masks a considerably more intricate socio-technical system, one whose inner workings are difficult to reconstruct. This lack of transparency appears systemic rather than incidental and posed a significant obstacle to the investigation underlying this report.

What could be deduced from available information is that ACS systems are not designed by single companies, but assembled through networks involving telecom operators, data brokers, algorithm developers, identity verification services, infrastructure providers, and payments platforms. As will be expanded upon in later sections, each of these actors plays a role in shaping both the datasets and the algorithmic tools through which credit decisions are ultimately produced. Yet these connections are rarely disclosed. Instead, they are often obscured behind vaguely worded Terms and Conditions or Privacy Notices that refer ambiguously to "third parties and partners" (Tala Loan App Kenya | App Privacy Policy & Customer Rights, n.d.), with

little indication of who these entities are or what data flows between them. The architecture of the system as a whole is thus concealed from public view.

Due to this, a shift in perspective was necessary. Instead of trying to access black-box decision pipelines, a data science approach was adopted, viewing credit scoring as a structured data journey along the lines of the framework proposed by Beaulieu and Leonelli (2022, 45). They describe data journeys as the movement of data through successive stages of data gathering, processing, and interpretation, each shaped by human decisions, technical choices, and institutional contexts that often remain invisible to one another. This framework provided a way to trace how credit scores are constructed, even when individual steps are not disclosed, by focusing on discrete, generalizable stages such as data collection, feature transformation, modelling, and score generation (Beaulieu and Leonelli, 2022, 45). It allowed inference of likely human choices embedded at each stage. *Figure 1* illustrates a simple view of the data journey that constitutes ACS and the variety of actors and data that are involved.¹

Figure 1: Simplified Overview of the Data to Score Journey.

¹ For example, Lendsquare, a platform operating across Nigeria, Kenya, and Rwanda that provides lending management systems (software enabling the creation and management of digital lending solutions), maintains an extensive network of integrated “providers.” These encompass all of the aforementioned company types, illustrating the diverse ecosystem of actors involved in assembling ACS systems (Lendsqr, n.d.-a).

By tracing the path from raw input to final score, our intention is to locate the points where responsibility resides, and to highlight the need for greater transparency, oversight, and care. These steps, and the ethical and technical tensions they involve, are examined in the sections that follow.

3.2. Data Gathering

This section examines the data practices of Lendtechs in Rwanda, Nigeria, and Kenya. It sheds light on current data gathering methodologies and highlights key points for potential intervention. Two important decisions were identified along our exploratory analysis of (1) What data is collected and why?, and (2) Who is accountable for data collection practices?

Five Lendtechs that use alternative data were analysed: Social Lender (Nigeria), Zowasel (Nigeria) (Zowasel, n.d.), Lendsquare (Nigeria) (Lendsqr, n.d.-b), Rubyx (Rwanda) (Rubyx, n.d.), and Tala (Kenya) (Tala, n.d.-b). Combining information on all five Lendtechs, we identified the range of sources of data collected, and characterised them according to form and purpose; the combined results appear in *Table 1*. An example of our working process for formulating *Tables 1 and 2* can be found in *Table 4* in the Appendix.

Table 1: Data Categories and Their Intended Purposes.

Metadata	Personal data	Social data	Digital financial data	Market specific	Traditional financial data
IP address	Name	Advertising interests	Mobile money transactions	Grower offers	Payment information
Log files	Address	Responses to direct marketing	Analytics	Transport offers	Bank details
Unique device identifiers	Email address	Opt-outs from direct marketing	Data warehouse inputs	Crop data	Card details
Pages viewed	Telephone number	Contact list from social media	Historic user data	Agronomic data	Purchase interest
Operating system	Date of birth	SMS logs	Repayment behavior	Land data	Credit information
Content of request	Employer	Call logs	Karma, prior loans	Satellite imagery data	Anonymized credit bureau data
Device type	Profession	Data shared via social media functions	CRM records	Grower management data	Black lists
Browser type and settings	Job title	Friends and family	E-commerce activity	Market info	Product holdings
Language settings	Age	Referees		Soil info	Account statements
Aggregate statistical information	Personal description	Guarantors		Yield forecast	Utility bill payments
Transferred volume of data	Photos and videos	Community social underwriting		Agronomy data	
Website requesting access	Customer enquiries	Connections on app			
SIM card info	Survey responses				
Device phone number	KYC (Know your customer)				
Behavior & tracking	Identification	Social Network Reliability	Digital money habits	Profitability assessment	Financial Assessment

Using the categories established in *Table 1*, we collated the forms of data and their sources by Lendtech company, with the results show in *Table 2*. Each colour of dot in *Table 2* represents a different Lendtech such that the table provides valuable insights into how each Lendtech collects data and helps identify potential patterns or definitions of creditworthiness. Different Lendtechs’ approached to assessing creditworthiness can be understood by analysing these patterns, as discussed in the following sections.

Table 2: Data Collection Types and Sources of Different Lendtechs. (Each colour dot represents a different Lendtech.)

SOURCE	Metadata	Traditional financial data	Personal data	Social data	Digital financial data	Market specific data
App	● ●		● ●	● ● ●	● ● ● ● ●	●
User		●	●	●		
Device	● ● ●			●		
Credit Bureau / Black Lists /Collection Agencies		● ● ●				
Id Verifier			●			
Natural Persons		●		●		
Social Media Apps				●		
Fintech Ecosystem		● ●			● ●	
Borrower's Bank		●				

3.2.1. Decision 1: What Data are Gathered and Why?

Opacity in Data Collection Practices

Our choice to analyse five Lendtechs was based on data availability, or rather the difficulty of gathering data from each Lendtech's website. For the majority of Lendtechs, their websites included a request for contact information to get in touch, but did not have information on data collection readily available. Instead, Lendtechs had privacy policies about the website itself, not their credit scoring practices.

In the cases where information was found, it lacked consistency and completeness. As an example, for Zowasel, no privacy policy was found, so the data collected are based on other information available on their website. For example, Zowasel claims to "utilize soil information, market information, yield forecasts, agronomy data, and farmers' KYC and conduct community social underwriting" (Zowasel, n.d.). However, the company's "Medium" blog page discussing "The Future of ACS For Digital Banks," points out that "ACS in essence, determines an individual's creditworthiness using non-traditional sources such as value chains, crop and agronomy data, harvest records, and digital footprints, rather than relying solely on traditional sources like debt repayment history or credit files" (Zowasel, 2023). There was no clarity regarding which of the two pages was accurate, or whether the data gathered were complete. A similar situation was found when we attempted to identify sources of data. This lack of consistency and completeness made it challenging to map what data are collected and where they come from.

Diverse and Inconsistent Creditworthiness Assessments

The definition of creditworthiness is key to understanding the justification behind the data collection process. Our categorization of data sources in *Table 2* was created as a result of not finding clear definitions of creditworthiness for any of the Lendtechs.

While no clear definitions or common data gathering patterns were found, various rationales were identified across Lendtechs. Insight into the logic behind data collection can be gained from these rationales, although they do not explain why certain data

decisions are preferred over others or the specific methods by which data are gathered and managed. For instance, a dedicated page for data ethics on Tala's website provided explanations regarding the ethical treatment of data. It states, "These data sources are selected to validate a customer's identity and determine loan eligibility. Only the necessary data is collected; previously, collection of data classes deemed unnecessary for underwriting was explicitly discontinued, and the necessity of collected data classes continues to be evaluated for such consideration" (Tala, n.d.-b). However, clarity on what constitutes the "necessary data" or the methods used to evaluate their necessity remain unexplained.

Bias and Inclusion Assessment

While the use of alternative data sources for assessing creditworthiness is primarily justified through the lens of promoting financial inclusion, a comprehensive examination of existing inequalities within the dataset itself was only discussed by one Lendtech and then only partially. Tala excludes data related to gender, race, ethnicity, religion, national origin, sexual orientation, disability, medical history, and political opinion from its creditworthiness assessments (Tala, n.d.-b). Other factors of exclusion like digital access or low literacy rates are not mentioned.

Another issue linked to ethical and inclusion assessments is the continued reliance on traditional financial data. While these data are still widely used by loan providers, how significantly they impact creditworthiness evaluations remains unclear. This uncertainty calls into question whether adopting alternative data genuinely benefit those previously excluded from financial services.

Ethical Implications

1. Lack of transparency

Numerous studies have found that transparency about the use and protection of consumers' data reinforces trust (Morey et al., n.d.). Additionally, facilitating users' understanding of the processes surrounding data collection and analysis would allow them to be more aware of these processes, potentially creating a sense of ownership,

causing them to seek more agency in the collection and analysis of their data (Pavlakos 2021, 50). Nevertheless, a significant lack of transparency in data gathering practices among Lendtechs was observed during our analysis.

While a lack of transparency may compromise trust and agency, it is crucial to consider the authoritative position Lendtech companies occupy within the lending business. Even were complete transparency achievable, the broader context in which alternative data is used to assess creditworthiness could not be ignored. Individuals often face constrained choices in regions with low digital literacy and high poverty rates. Here, Rational Choice Theory helps explain why people may still opt into services with unfavourable terms: When the need for access to credit outweighs concerns about data gathering practices, even a “bad” option becomes the rational one. For someone living in poverty, the urgency of securing a loan can replace the ability, or opportunity, to critically evaluate the risks of non-transparent systems.

As (Pavlakos 2021, 51) points out, the issue is not just a question about how users can increase their agency when it comes to understanding and claiming ownership of their data, but also how corporations can change their policies to better reflect users’ interests. In this sense, transparency becomes key in fostering a trusting and fair AI ecosystem in countries like Rwanda.

2. Lack of definitions

The lack of definitions of creditworthiness reflects the role of big data in the financial sector. The emergence of big data represents an important moment when innovative methods of interpreting big datasets have become possible. This change allows for the collection, storage, and sharing of datasets in ways that facilitate advanced analytical techniques in addition to allowing for data collection to be considered retrospectively (Andrejevic & Gates, 2014, 186,187).

These new practices of data gathering reflect a problematic belief in the objectivity of numbers and a mistaken perception of data as the essence of social reality. With the inherent opacity of data science methods, the core issue is not merely about trusting

institutions, but about maintaining confidence in the integrity of the data ecosystem (Andrejevic & Gates, 2014, 193). Regardless of the size of the data, big data practices are subject to limitations and biases. Without those biases and limitations being understood and outlined, misinterpretation may result (Boyd & Crawford, 2012, 668).

In this context, definitions gain importance due to the need for justified data collection and agency within the assessment of creditworthiness. Once we recognize that neither the big volume of data nor the novel methods of gathering and analysing it inherently lead to more accurate assessments of creditworthiness, it is possible to take a step back. This opens the door to exploring alternative approaches for obtaining reliable insights into risk and creditworthiness, without relying on assumptions or subjecting users to unfair treatment.

3.2.2. Decision 2: Who is Accountable for Data Gathering Practices?

Two Scenarios of Data Processing

Lendtechs utilizing alternative data operate through two primary models. First, Lendtechs that serve as loan providers develop their own algorithms and manage data collection directly (see *Figure 2*). In this model, they establish relationships with various institutions to gather diverse data points. For instance, Social Lender uses its proprietary algorithm to perform a social audit of the user on mobile, online, offline, and social platforms and gives a Social Reputation Score to each user. They retrieve user data based on authorized access granted by the user (Social Lender Nigeria, n.d.). In a similar way, Tala determines the weights of individual data points using state-of-the-art machine learning techniques, trained on historic user data (Tala, n.d.-b).

Figure 2: Data Processing Scenario 1. (Lendtechs that serve as loan providers develop their own algorithms and manage data collection directly.)

Second, non-financial Lendtechs function as technology providers to loan providers. These firms specialize in developing credit scoring algorithms and in data collection. In this scenario, the responsibility and agency for data gathering and model development shift to a third-party provider. As a first example, Lendsqr provides end-to-end loan management software and also gives loan providers access to a massive data ecosystem of borrowers within Lendsqr to make credit decisions; this is described as “similar to credit bureau data but on steroids” (Lendsqr, n.d.-b). In a similar way, Zowasel bridges the gap between agribusinesses and financial institutions to make quick lending decisions in a low-risk, cost-effective, and efficient manner by deploying their proprietary ACS System (ACCESS) to score and make repayment predictions (Zowasel, n.d.).

The second scenario brings additional complexity regarding data access and sharing, as seen in *Figure 3*. Companies like Lendsqr, Rubyx, and Zowasel also provide access to what we will call a data ecosystem. Zowasel, for example, enables farmer organizations to digitize farmer data and automate value chain processes, including cultivation, farm details, profiles, behavioural biometrics, harvest, income, and sales records. ACCESS transforms this data into actionable insights, providing financial institutions with convenient access to farmers’ data, enabling creditworthiness checks, “know your customer” (KYC) verification, and lending decisions (Ikwegbue, 2023). In this sense, the access and sharing of data goes beyond the loan service provider and becomes part of this data ecosystem.

Figure 3: Data Processing Scenario 2. (Non-financial Lendtechs develop the algorithms and manage data collection as a service provided to loan providers.)

Ethical Implications

When examining the two ACS scenarios, important implications regarding responsibility and accountability emerge at different levels. In the first scenario, where loan providers develop the algorithm and define the data collection process, accountability is already challenged by the opacity and complexity inherent in data gathering, processing, and analysis. These processes are rarely made transparent, and the distributed nature of data science makes it difficult to trace specific decisions back to individual actors.

The distributed nature of data science seems to create insurmountable problems for any attempt to identify responsibilities for specific implications of technical decisions taken when processing data, and thus to make individuals accountable for the ethical significance of their actions. (Leonelli, 2016, 6)

Users are typically not given the means to evaluate the consequences of their decisions in the moment they make them, nor are mechanisms available to uncover the complex interdependencies involved in a given data journey.

In the second scenario, where third-party providers offer algorithmic models as a service, responsibility for data gathering and algorithm development is automatically shifted to these external actors. This transfer introduces a double layer of accountability failure: first, due to the nature of big data itself, where context is often lost and interpretation becomes difficult at scale, “managing context [becomes] an ongoing challenge” (Boyd & Crawford, 2012, 671), and second, because responsibility is

distributed across multiple entities. “Attempts to retain a ‘control zone’ in which research datasets [...] can be evaluated by relevant experts [...] are failing” due to the variety of locations and processing methods involved (Leonelli, 2016, 2). Under such conditions, accountability becomes even harder to enforce, and “with the question of responsibility comes the question of accountability, i.e., who stands up for decisions made with and around AI and its trustworthiness” (Hohma, 2024, 13).

Furthermore, the second scenario introduces additional privacy and user trust risks, as it connects loan providers to broader data ecosystems managed by third-party Lendtechs. In this arrangement, agency is lost not only in the initial data gathering and algorithmic development but also in the future use and contextualization of the data. Data collected for credit scoring purposes can be repurposed across various domains without users’ awareness or consent. As noted, “data collected by a particular application can often be repurposed for a variety of uses”, and this repurposing is not incidental but structurally embedded in the logic of big data (Andrejevic & Gates, 2014, 189). This phenomenon, “function creep,” undermines user trust and safety by enabling continuous reinterpretation of personal data in contexts far removed from their original creation, making accountability even more difficult to evaluate.

The control zone, the zone of agency and responsibility, must be kept as small and clearly defined as possible to address these challenges. This would allow for more direct lines of accountability and reduce the ethical ambiguity when responsibility is distributed across opaque systems. As noted, “accountability consists of two components, responsibility and satisfactory explanation” (Hohma, 2024, 14). Without mechanisms to ensure that actors within the Lendtech ecosystem can rationally justify their behaviour, responsibility and accountability remain a challenge.

The way that Lendtechs work entails more than just how data is processed; it hints at more profound considerations of trust, responsibility, and who gets to shape the concepts of creditworthiness. However, the data journey does not end there. The design of algorithms carries its own set of ethical choices, often quietly embedding assumptions, trade-offs, and biases that ripple outward. It becomes evident that

technical decisions are never neutral, but are shaped by, and in turn shape, the social values and power structures within which they operate.

3.3. Algorithm Design

Once data have been collected and processed, the next step in the ACS process is to use that data to generate a score. This is accomplished through algorithms. An algorithm, in this context, is a set of rules and statistical processes that takes a borrower's data as input and produces a credit score or a loan decision as output. This includes AI models. While the previous section highlighted the opacity surrounding data collection practices, this challenge is even more pronounced when examining the algorithms themselves. During our research, it quickly became clear that Fintech companies are often highly secretive about the technical details of their proprietary models, frequently treating them as a core part of their competitive advantage. Publicly available information is typically limited to high-level descriptions, such as the general type of algorithm used.

However, this lack of transparency does not prevent a critical analysis. Drawing on established principles of data science and machine learning, we can identify at least some fundamental decisions that every Lendtech firm must make when designing and training its scoring algorithm. These decisions are not purely technical, but are deeply entwined with ethical tensions. This section deconstructs this process by focusing on three key decision points: the choice of model type, the potential use of explainability techniques, and the definition of "success" for the algorithm. Each decision involves navigating the inherent tension between business objectives, such as maximizing predictive accuracy and profit, and the broader societal goals of fairness, transparency, and financial inclusion.

3.3.1. Decision 1: Choosing the Model Type

The first and perhaps most consequential decision a developer makes is what type of model to use. This choice is fundamental because it places the resulting algorithm on a spectrum between transparency and opacity. The model's position on this spectrum

directly influences how easily its decisions can be understood, explained, audited, or challenged by users, regulators, and even the company’s internal teams.

On one end of the spectrum are transparent or “white-box” models. These models operate in a way that is inherently intelligible to a human expert. A prime example is the decision tree. A decision tree makes predictions by following a series of simple, conditional rules based on the input data. The path to any given decision can be visually traced and logically understood. Some Fintech firms explicitly choose this path. For instance, Rubyx, a provider in Rwanda, states that it uses “configurable decision trees,” which allows for a clear understanding of the decision-making logic (Rubyx, n.d.).

Figure 4: An Example of a Decision Tree from the Rubyx Website. (From “Rubyx Solutions” by Rubyx, n.d. (<https://www.rubyx.io/solutions/>), Retrieved July 11, 2025).)

Figure 4 provides a simplified illustration from Rubyx’s website, while Figure 7 shows a more detailed example—from a different context—of how a decision tree classifier works. The highlighted path in Figure 5 clearly shows the specific sequence of rules that led the model to its final prediction, making the logic transparent and contestable.

Figure 5: A Decision Tree Classifier Trained on a Breast Cancer Dataset. (The orange line shows how the model reached a certain prediction. From “InterpretML Documentation” by InterpretML Contributors, n.d. (<https://interpret.ml/docs/index.html>, Retrieved March 11, 2024).)

On the other end of the spectrum are opaque or “black-box” models, such as complex neural networks or proprietary ensemble methods. These models can identify incredibly subtle and complex patterns in data, often leading to higher predictive accuracy. However, their internal workings are so intricate that it is practically impossible for a human to understand how they arrive at a specific conclusion. Many prominent Fintechs opt for these more powerful models. Tala in Kenya refers to its use of “state-of-the-art machine learning models,” (Tala, n.d.-b) and Lendsqr in Nigeria employs a proprietary “Lendsqr ML engine” (Lendsqr, n.d.-b), both of which suggest the use of complex, opaque systems. The choice between a transparent and an opaque model represents a direct trade-off between interpretability and predictive accuracy. As shown in *Figure 6*, simpler models like decision trees are highly interpretable but may be less accurate, while more complex models like neural networks tend to be more accurate but far less interpretable (Morocho-Cayamcela et al., 2019, 137200). The business incentive to choose a more accurate black-box model is strong, as improvements in predicting loan defaults could have a positive impact on profitability.

Figure 6: The Trade-off between Interpretability and Accuracy of Some Relevant ML Models. (From “Machine Learning for 5G/B5G Mobile and Wireless Communications: Potential, Limitations, and Future Directions” by M. E. Morocho-Cayamcela, H. Lee, and W. Lim, 2019, *IEEE Access*, 7, p. 137200. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2019.2942390>)

Ethical Implications of Model Choice

The decision to use an opaque black-box model carries significant ethical implications. First, it creates a barrier for consumers. If an individual is denied a loan by an opaque system, it is difficult to provide them with a clear and actionable reason for the rejection. This hinders the user’s ability to contest an unfair or inaccurate decision and prevents them from understanding what steps they could take to improve their financial standing and succeed in a future application (Umeaduma & Adedapo, 2025, 6648). This opacity also presents a major challenge for regulation. Frameworks like Europe’s GDPR have established a “right to explanation,” mandating that individuals receive “meaningful information about the logic involved” in automated decisions that significantly affect them (Rizzi et al., 2021, 18). While equivalent regulations are still under development in

many African jurisdictions, for example the “Data Protection and Privacy Law” in Rwanda (Baig & Khan, 2021), the principle of transparency is a cornerstone of responsible AI. Meeting this standard with a black-box model is exceptionally difficult.

Furthermore, black-box models can be accurate for the wrong reasons. The model might learn a shortcut or pattern that exists only in the training and test data, causing it to fail when used in the real world (Lapuschkin et al., 2019, 2). A black-box model can also make discriminatory decisions even if protected characteristics like ethnicity or gender are removed. It is possible for powerful models to infer them from other data like postcodes (Veale & Binns, 2017, 4). Without transparency, it is extremely difficult to audit a model to ensure it does not rely on spurious or biased correlations. This aspect is highly relevant to the companies who develop these algorithms. However, an argument can be made in favour of automated black-box systems. Proponents, including Tala, suggest that they can reduce the human-based discrimination that has long plagued traditional lending. They argue that applicants are often “more comfortable being scored by a machine” because it removes the potential for the “in-person biases of bank lending officials” to influence the decision (Tala, n.d.-b). This view argues that even an imperfect algorithm may be fairer than a biased human loan officer, which downplays the risk of bias being encoded in the model itself.

3.3.2. Decision 2: Employing Explainable AI (XAI) as a Mitigation Strategy

If a company chooses to use an opaque black-box model, it faces a subsequent decision: whether to employ Explainable AI (XAI) techniques to mitigate the model’s inherent opacity. XAI does not make the black box itself transparent. Instead, it uses secondary models, or “explainers,” to generate post-hoc explanations of why a specific decision was made. This is a strategy to provide at least some insight into the model’s behaviour without sacrificing the predictive power of the complex algorithm.

Common XAI techniques, such as LIME and SHAP, are model-agnostic, meaning they can be applied to virtually any black-box model to generate “local” explanations (Bodria

et al., 2023, 1724). A local explanation highlights which features (e.g., income, app usage patterns, number of contacts) were most influential in a single credit decision. *Figure 7* shows how LIME explains a prediction by identifying the key features that contributed to it. This type of explanation is called “feature importance.”

Figure 7: A Visualization Created by the LIME Library Explaining a Tabular Classifier that Predicts Whether a Mushroom is Edible or Poisonous. (From “Lime: Explaining the predictions of any machine learning classifier” by M. T. C. Ribeiro, n.d., LIME GitHub (<https://github.com/marcotcr/lime>, Retrieved March 11, 2024).)

Another explanation type is counterfactuals, which are statements that show how a decision could be changed. For example: “You were denied a loan because your annual income was £30,000. If your income had been £45,000, you would have been offered a loan” (Wachter et al., 2018, 5).

A central question surrounding XAI is who gets to see these explanations. If they are used only by internal development and audit teams, they can serve as a powerful tool to probe for potential biases and debug the model’s logic. If they are provided to regulators, they can facilitate oversight. If they are shared with consumers, they can help fulfil the “right to explanation” and empower users. Each choice has different implications for accountability and transparency.

Ethical Implications of Using XAI

The use of XAI offers clear benefits. It can help Fintech companies meet regulatory demands for transparency and allow internal auditors to investigate whether the model is behaving as intended (Umeaduma & Adedapo, 2025, 6655). However, XAI is not a silver bullet and comes with its own set of ethical risks.

A primary concern is that XAI explanations can be misleading or inaccurate. The explainer is a separate model trying to approximate the logic of the primary black-box model. If this approximation is poor, the explanation can misrepresent why a decision was made, potentially lending a false sense of legitimacy and authority to an unjust or flawed system (Rudin et al., 2022, 2).

Another concern is that if explanations are provided to consumers, they might “game the system.” That is, individuals might alter their behaviour solely to obtain a loan, rather than to demonstrate genuine creditworthiness (Rizzi et al., 2021, 19). For example, if a user learns that having more contacts in their phone leads to a higher score, they might artificially add contacts. However, the risk of such manipulation can be viewed differently. First, if a metric like the number of contacts can be faked so easily, it is probably a poor measure of creditworthiness to begin with. Second, and more importantly, transparency can help improve financial literacy. When people understand the real factors that lead to a decision, they can take meaningful steps to improve their financial health, which benefits both them and the lender.

Ultimately, XAI should be viewed as an imperfect tool for managing the risks of black-box models, not a complete solution. Its use is a trade-off between providing some insight versus having none.

3.3.3. Decision 3: Defining Success

Before an algorithm is trained, its developers must make a crucial decision: what does “success” look like? In other words, what objective is the algorithm being optimized to achieve? This choice fundamentally shapes the model's behaviour and, consequently, its societal impact. This decision often embodies the core tension between a company's business goals and its stated social mission.

The most common business objective for a credit scoring model is predictive accuracy, specifically minimizing the loan default rate to maximize profit (Umeaduma & Adedapo, 2025, 6652). An algorithm optimized solely for this goal will learn to identify the

applicants with the lowest possible risk of non-repayment, based on the historical data it is trained on.

However, a company may choose to balance this objective with a social mission, such as promoting financial inclusion. This requires a different definition of success. For example, one Asian Fintech firm made a conscious decision to lower its approval thresholds for female applicants. Management knew this would likely lead to a higher default rate among this group in the short term, but they accepted this risk as a necessary investment to build a more representative dataset and actively promote the inclusion of women in the long run (Rizzi et al., 2021, 17). This demonstrates that defining success is not just a technical exercise but a strategic choice about a company's values and priorities.

Ethical Implications of Defining Success

The choice of an optimization metric has profound ethical implications. Optimizing for a simple, easily measurable Key Performance Indicator (KPI), like the loan repayment rate, can lead to a phenomenon known as “Goodhart’s Law”: when a measure becomes a target, it ceases to be a good measure (Strathern, 1997, 308). The system’s behaviour may drift away from its original, broader purpose, such as financial inclusion, in pursuit of the narrow, quantifiable goal.

This tension is visible in the operations of many Lendtechs. Tala, for example, has a stated purpose of expanding financial inclusion (High, 2023). However, this purpose may conflict with the growth-oriented KPIs prioritized by its investors, who may be more focused on metrics like low customer acquisition costs and rapid expansion (Rizzi et al., 2021, 26). Actively pursuing inclusion, as the Asian Fintech example shows, may require a company and its investors to accept lower short-term profits or higher initial default rates. This highlights a direct conflict between investor pressure for immediate returns and the time and resources needed to build fair, equitable, and genuinely inclusive models.

Ultimately, defining fairness and success is a social and ethical question, not merely a technical one. This places a heavy burden on data scientists and developers, who may not be equipped or empowered to make such value-laden judgments alone. As one data scientist involved in these systems expressed:

I feel quite strongly that just because I'm the person implementing these things doesn't mean that I should be the person deciding them. (Quoted in Rizzi et al., 2021, 20)

This sentiment underscores the critical need for broader, more diverse input in the design process. Making these decisions effectively requires deep local knowledge of the social, cultural, and economic context in which the algorithm will be deployed. A lack of diversity on development teams can lead to significant oversights, where incorrect assumptions about a population lead to biased or exclusionary systems (Rizzi et al., 2021, 5). The definition of success, therefore, must be a collaborative process that reflects the values and needs of the communities the technology is supposed to serve.

3.4. Concluding Remarks: Data Management

This section has examined the implementation of AI-driven ACS in African Lendtech ecosystems through the lens of the data journey, with particular attention to practices observable in Rwanda, Kenya, and Nigeria. By focusing on two critical junctures, alternative data collection and algorithm design, the analysis aimed to understand how creditworthiness is actually determined in practice, and to highlight the ethical problems that arise from the way these systems are built and used.

The investigation into data collection practices revealed a highly fragmented and non-transparent landscape. Across the Lendtech sector, companies employ divergent approaches to gathering alternative data, with limited transparency regarding what data is collected, how it is sourced, or why it is deemed relevant. Notably, no Lendtech examined in this study publicly offered a working definition of creditworthiness or articulated how specific data points contribute to such assessments. This lack of clarity has important implications for user agency. Without access to meaningful information about the data being collected and its purpose, users are unable to engage with these

services in an informed manner or take steps to improve their own standing within the system. In effect, this limits their ability to participate in the co-construction of more meaningful and representative data practices.

These concerns are particularly pronounced in the context of financially vulnerable populations, who often lack viable alternatives and may accept intrusive or poorly explained data practices out of necessity. The imbalance of power between Lendtech providers and users is exacerbated by the scale and granularity of data collected, raising questions about proportionality and data minimization. The extent to which providers rely on broad, indiscriminate data harvesting, rather than curated, high-quality data, warrants further scrutiny.

Adding to these issues is the distributed nature of data flows within the digital lending ecosystem. Multiple actors, ranging from telecommunications providers and data brokers to software vendors and infrastructure providers, contribute to the systems that generate credit scores. This decentralization effectively disperses accountability and makes enforcement challenging. In such a context, foundational elements of ethical governance (traceability, responsibility, and explainability) are significantly weakened. Users are left without clear avenues for redress, and regulators face systemic barriers to oversight.

In the second stage of the analysis, attention turned to algorithm design. Three dimensions were highlighted: model selection, explainability, and the definition of algorithmic success. The choice between black-box and white-box models entails a persistent tension between predictive performance and interpretability. While more complex models may deliver higher accuracy, they do so at the expense of transparency, thereby impeding efforts to contest, audit, or understand algorithmic decisions. This lack of explainability not only further limits individual recourse but also hinders regulatory capacity to assess fairness or systemic bias.

Nevertheless, the use of algorithmic systems in credit scoring is not intrinsically problematic. Properly designed, such systems offer the potential to reduce human bias and enhance consistency. Tools such as XAI represent a promising avenue for making

these systems more transparent and user-facing, with potential benefits for financial literacy and empowerment. Yet these gains remain conditional on the underlying assumptions, data, and metrics embedded within each model.

The final analytic concern centred on how success is defined within algorithmic systems. Here, the prioritization of commercial performance metrics over broader social considerations emerged as a critical tension. The selection of optimization targets, whether focused on economic or social goals, fundamentally shapes outcomes. In doing so, it embeds the values and strategic priorities of system designers into the architecture of decision-making. This is not a neutral process, and its implications for inclusion, equity, and fairness deserve explicit consideration.

Taken together, these findings point to the inadequacy of consent-based models of data governance in the context of digital credit scoring. The complexity and lack of transparency in ACS systems make it nearly impossible for users to give truly informed consent. Users cannot meaningfully evaluate the implications of data processing activities they do not, and often cannot, understand. As such, the risk is that regulatory frameworks grounded solely in user consent will legitimate ethically problematic and structurally opaque practices. Medine and Murthy even argue that consent-based regulation protects companies more than it does users (Medine & Murthy, 2020, 7).

Following recommendations made by Medine and Murthy, Rwanda might be able to carve out a leadership role in the governance of AI and Fintech by moving its regulatory efforts beyond procedural notions of consent toward more substantive models of data responsibility. This includes articulating clear standards for legitimate purpose, ensuring proportionality in data collection, and introducing fiduciary obligations for those who design and deploy algorithmic systems and are involved in the processing of data (Medine & Murthy, 2020, 9-12). Regulatory approaches must also strengthen requirements for explainability, fairness auditing, and redress mechanisms to ensure that digital lending systems operate in a manner consistent with principles of accountability and social justice.

4. Risks

Our consideration of risks is separated into four parts. We initially provide a market overview of the Fintech ecosystems in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda. At the core of our research, four core risk areas are analysed: risks to fairness, privacy violations, cybersecurity threats, and external control. Then, we introduce the regulatory and policy context around Fintech, AI governance, and data protection. Finally, the discussion synthesizes the findings and reflects on broader lessons for emerging Fintech markets.

4.1. Overview of the Fintech Landscape in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda

Fintech services encompass various categories from personal finance to insurance, blockchain, and virtual currencies (Magdy, 2024). However, as this section of the report aims to highlight the risks that Fintech poses for end consumers, we primarily focus here on Fintech firms in the following two categories:

1. **Digital Lending:** Digital lending platforms provide instant credit entirely via digital platforms. They include peer-to-peer marketplace lending, mobile-based loans, microloans, and Buy Now Pay Later systems (OECD, 2024). In addition to lending based on traditional measures of creditworthiness, such as formal credit history or proof of steady income, many Fintech companies use AI-supported scoring models based on alternative data for their assessment (Omotubora, 2024). This data includes mobile transaction history, spending categories, and even smartphone data such as contact list diversity, call histories, GPS data, and battery charging habits (OptimusAI, n.d; Jemutai, 2025).
2. **Digital Payment:** Digital payment platforms enable sending and receiving money via digital peer-to-peer transfers, merchant payments, bill-pay, and e-wallets using mobile phones (Dudu et al., 2024).

Kenya leads Sub-Saharan Africa's Fintech industry, particularly in mobile money adoption, with platforms such as M-Pesa that have significantly expanded financial

inclusion (Musamali et al., 2024; Klapper et al., 2025). M-Pesa alone is one of the most popular financial tools among Kenyan users, accounting for over 34 million customers generating 30 billion transactions in 2024 (Ndege, 2025). But Nigeria has rapidly caught up. Nigeria is Africa's largest Fintech market and home to approximately 430 Fintech companies as of early 2025, accounting for 31% of the country's startup funding (Klapper et al., 2025). While these two are the continent's biggest Fintech industries, Rwanda is an emerging hub with strong state support and a focus on responsible AI (Ministry of ICT and Innovation, 2022). Its 2024–2029 national Fintech strategy (see Section 5.1) aims to create 7,500 jobs and attract \$200 million in investment (Republic of Rwanda, 2024). Hosting the Inclusive Fintech Forum 2025 in Kigali further reflects its ambition to lead regional innovation (Global Finance & Technology Network, 2025).

To examine these countries' Fintech landscape, we conducted a market scan to better understand the most relevant Fintech providers in digital lending and credit, as well as digital payments and money transfer for each country. The resulting overview in *Figure 8* includes both household names and infrastructure-critical platforms, arranged by Fintech category and country.

Figure 8: Overview of Relevant Fintech Providers in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda.²

Country	Digital Lending & Credit	Digital Payments & Transfer
Kenya		
Nigeria		
Rwanda		

4.2. Risks around Fintech

The following section examines how Fintech technologies risk fairness, privacy, cybersecurity, and local control. In order to contextualize the abstract concerns in lived experiences, each risk at the core of our paper is introduced with a short fictionalized

² This market overview was compiled from internet searches of publicly available sources, including company websites, informal popularity rankings, app download statistics, and platforms such as Crunchbase. Many of the sources lacked methodological transparency and some were even published by the Fintech providers themselves, frequently placing their own platforms at the top. In addition, the sources were sometimes contradictory, with discrepancies in company headquarters, user numbers, and perceived relevance. Where contradictions or clear favouritism occurred, we prioritized consistency across multiple sources and rectified outdated information. The categories “Digital Lending & Credit” and “Digital Payments & Transfer” were established based on recurring classifications in Fintech literature and reflect the services most relevant to everyday financial access for users in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda. Due to these limitations, this overview should be understood as an illustrative snapshot rather than an exhaustive representation of the sector.

“risk story.” As inspiration for these stories, we used real-world reports and possible current and future developments.

4.2.1. Risking Fairness

Fintech systems may risk fairness through mechanisms of exclusion, embedding discriminatory biases, and enabling harassment. For the last, we explicitly address aggressive debt collection as a form of harassment, but do not cover all aspects of consumer protection, such as high interest rates.

Exclusion

With the following fictionalized story, we illustrate how digital financial systems can perpetuate and deepen existing structural inequalities.

Amina lives in Kibera, Nairobi, and belongs to Kenya’s Nubian community, a minority. One day, she fell ill and needed money to buy medicine. She turned to the mobile loan apps, but each required a national ID. Despite applying multiple times, her application for a national ID was rejected due to lack of a birth certificate, which she had no way of obtaining. Without it, Amina could not access any loan apps. She borrowed what she could from a neighbour and rationed the rest, feeling not only sick but excluded.³

Amina’s story highlights an important risk of Fintech: Despite its promise of financial inclusion, it is not a panacea and may reinforce exclusion of already marginalized groups due to broader structural barriers.

³ The story is loosely based on the real-life experience of Ziya, a Kenyan woman from the Nubian community, as documented in a Wired article (Maru et al., 2020). While specific details have been adapted for narrative clarity, the exclusionary consequences for marginalized communities of lacking a national ID are drawn directly from her account. The added loan component and connection to problems with ID proof draws inspiration from reporting (Okata, 2023) on how Kenyan LGBTQ+ entrepreneurs are denied access to formal credit because their gender doesn’t match their ID’s. Fintech systems that require formal identification are, for example, the widely used loan providers as Tala, branch or stawi, as they specify on their respective websites.

Exclusion is not a problem specific to Fintech, but limited access to financial services generally affects a large portion of the population of Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda. This exclusion often stems from missing requirements like proof of identity, as illustrated in our story, or a lack of traditional factors of creditworthiness, which, as mentioned above, include formal credit histories or proof of steady income (Omotubora, 2024). Fintech platforms can replicate these exclusion patterns by relying on similar forms of data.

To counter this, Fintech companies have introduced alternative credit scoring models, as described in the market overview above (OECD, 2024). But they not only bear risks to transparency, privacy, and of bias, but also rely on digital infrastructure and footprints that are not available for everyone (Omotubora, 2024). Access to Fintech can, for example, be hindered through limited internet access and limited phone or smartphone ownership. In Nigeria, for example, while mobile phone adoption reached 93% in 2023, only 27% of users owned a smartphone (EFInA, 2023).

Even when access exists, lacking digital and financial literacy can remain a serious barrier to the effective use of Fintech, especially considering the comparatively low reported financial literacy rates⁴ of 62% in Kenya, 40% in Nigeria, and 53% in Rwanda (Kenya Bankers Association, n.d.; OECD, 2024; Omotubora, 2024; Owolabi, n.d.; Utembinema et al., 2022). This lack of knowledge, together with insufficient transparency and disclosure of Fintech companies, may lead uninformed lenders to make decisions that work against their best interests and result in financially vulnerable borrowers falling into debt cycles caused by high interest rates, extra fees, and loan rollovers (OECD, 2024).

Due to these barriers, already marginalized groups such as women or rural populations are especially affected by financial exclusion (EFInA, 2023; National Financial Inclusion Steering Committee, 2022a, 2022c; Omotubora, 2024). Since the result of financial

⁴ There are no official numbers provided by public institutes for statistics or governmental institutions. Rates vary and are highly dependent on the definition of financial literacy. The referenced resources do not contain further information on how these rates were measured and why they may be unreliable. Therefore, these rates should only be used as an indication of a possible problem that is widely discussed in literature.

exclusion is potentially to limits opportunities at a large scale, it risks not only creating social instability and worsening income inequality and poverty, but can also exclude people socially, politically, and economically (Bekele, 2022; Smith, 2025).

In sum, Fintech is often framed as a significant enabler of financial inclusion, but it still bears the risk of reinforcing structural inequalities when infrastructure issues and exclusionary factors are not considered.

Discriminatory Bias

Overcoming infrastructural barriers is only a first step. As Fintech platforms increasingly integrate AI and automated decision-making, they introduce a new dimension of exclusion: algorithmic bias, as demonstrated in the following fictional story.

Zuri and her husband run a small food store together in Mombasa. Every day, they receive payments through mobile money and take turns paying suppliers. Their income and spending patterns are nearly identical. However, when Zuri checks her credit limit on their mobile payment and loan app, she is shocked to find hers is twenty times lower than her husband's. The app offers no explanation or breakdown of how the limit is calculated; it only notes that the credit limit is evaluated with the help of AI. When Zuri applies for a small business loan to purchase additional stock, the app rejects her, since the amount exceeds her low limit. Her husband, with a much higher limit, is approved instantly.⁵

This example illustrates what research has identified: that systems with AI can have discriminatory biases.

⁵ The risk narrative is loosely inspired by a widely discussed incident involving Apple Card credit limit discrepancies (e.g. Hansson, 2021), and testimonies of similar cases shared in the corresponding comment thread on X about the incident (Hansson, 2019). However, due to the opaque nature of many AI systems and the lack of transparency in automated decision-making processes, real-world and particularly context-specific examples in Kenya, Rwanda, or Nigeria of bias are difficult to identify, document, or verify, so the story remains largely fiction by the authors. Additional background is provided by reports of gender bias in lending more broadly, such as the stories of challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in India (Singh, 2024) and Nigeria (Moniepoint, n.d.). However, the latter did not directly inform the fictional narrative.

Generally, we can differentiate between two types of biases: data bias and algorithmic bias. Data bias in AI arises where training data reflects historical and societal inequalities or underrepresents certain groups, resulting in lower accuracy for individuals from those groups (Elly, 2025; Smith, 2025). Because data are not neutral or objective, systems often inherit the biases of prior decision-makers or mirror systemic injustices embedded in credit systems (Barocas & Selbst, 2016; Chapman, 2021; Smith, 2025). Algorithmic bias, on the other hand, means that the model design and development choices are shaped by the values, perspectives, and priorities of the creators and their institutions, and possibly amplify disparities, as noted in the previous section (Elly, 2025; Smith, 2025). This can be especially problematic in the technology field, where a widely recognized lack of diversity, especially in positions of ownership and power, can lead to the creators' definition of concepts, such as creditworthiness, being embedded into Fintech systems (Smith, 2025).

The problem of bias is further compounded by the opaqueness of AI systems; as discussed above, their complex, "black-box" nature often obscures how decisions are made and hinders transparency, external evaluation, and accountability (Chapman, 2021; Smith, 2025). This makes it difficult to detect or correct embedded disparities.

Nevertheless, the beliefs that technology and algorithms are objective, data reflect truth, and, consequently, machine learning can eliminate "subjective" human biases from decision making, are widespread, especially among developers and Fintech actors (Barocas & Selbst, 2016; Chapman, 2021; Smith, 2025). This view does not consider the context and the human choices behind the algorithm and data (Smith, 2025). The consequence is an "objective algorithm paradox": Fintech firms may have good intentions and set financial inclusion as their goal; however, the belief that the technology is objective can result in the perpetuation of existing biases and underlying structural inequalities (Chapman, 2021; Smith, 2025). In practice, this belief can often lead to the exclusion of protected attributes like gender and race under a "blind" and agnostic model (Smith, 2025). However, since AI can use seemingly neutral data points as proxies for protected classifications, this "blind" approach obscures disparities rather

than addressing the inequalities directly, which Fintech companies do not see as part of their responsibilities (Chapman, 2021; Smith, 2025).

Ultimately, the resulting discriminatory bias can significantly impact inclusion in financial services and entrench and amplify societal biases and systemic inequalities in the long term, even when human biases change (Elly, 2025; Smith, 2025).

Harassment

Another way of risking fairness is harassment, as the following story shows.

Sani, an electrician in Abuja, took out a small loan from a digital lending app to cover transport costs. When a family emergency delayed repayment, he received threatening messages warning of defamation if he did not pay the same day. He explained his situation to the loan company and promised repayment within two days. Nonetheless, by the next morning, over one hundred of his contacts, including family, friends, and professional connections, received messages calling Sani unreliable and a fraudster, and claiming that he stole money from the loan company. Though he repaid the loan that same day and asked the company to retract its claims, the damage was done. After that, some clients cancelled their orders because of trust issues, and some relatives asked him why he brought shame to the family. He felt disgraced and compromised.⁶

Sani's story illustrates a risk that many people face in real life: harassment when debt is collected aggressively through intimidation and humiliation (Jalal-Eddeen, 2025). Since high default rates are a challenge for digital lending, companies take steps to force repayment through various, sometimes aggressive recovery tactics (Adaramola et al., 2021; Jalal-Eddeen, 2025). These include persistent calls, messages, public shaming through social media posts, and contacting borrowers' networks (Adaramola et al., 2021; Jalal-Eddeen, 2025; Sommer et al., 2025). Using these practices, Fintech companies frame defaults as criminal acts and use social disgrace and defamation as

⁶ This story is inspired by cases and testimonies in Jalal-Eddeen (2024) and Abba (2021).

tools (Adaramola et al., 2021). Personal information and relationships become exploited and capitalized upon for debt collection, which ultimately infringes upon the fundamental right of human dignity (Adaramola et al., 2021; Donovan & Park, 2022; Jalal-Eddeen, 2025). The adoption of technologies like AI and chatbots allows harassment to be automated, enables the personalization of aggressive debt collection strategies on a large scale, and ultimately, aggravates the overall risks (Chapman, 2021; Yahiya & Ahmad, 2024). Kaur and Ilavarasan (2021) highlight limited or absent regulatory oversight and enforcement, and limited digital literacy as contributing factors to this risk.

The consequences of such harassment for an individual can be severe. It can not only impact an individual's work, as in our risk story, but also cause feelings of abuse, embarrassment, and psychological distress that can go as far as suicide (Donovan & Park, 2022; Jalal-Eddeen, 2025; Sommer et al., 2025). Furthermore, it can lead to isolation of the indebted person because of internal or external shame (Donovan & Park, 2022). Finally, aggressive debt collection violates users' and third parties' privacy and rights to data protection (Adaramola et al., 2021).

4.2.2. Risking Privacy

This leads us to the next risk area: privacy. To demonstrate its implications, we turn to the fictional story of Daniel, a teacher in Nakuru.

Daniel was caught off guard when he received an intimidating phone call from an online loan company. An employee claimed he needed to repay a friend's debt because he had allegedly been registered as the guarantor. Although Daniel and his friend never agreed to it, a credit app accessed the friend's contacts without permission and baselessly listed Daniel as a guarantor. In the following days, the harassment continued. Daniel received repeated reminder calls and threatening text messages, despite having no connection to the loan. As his contact

*information had been used for external purposes, he saw his privacy violated and tried to investigate.*⁷

Daniel's story emphasizes the risk of privacy and data protection problems in the Fintech sectors in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda, particularly regarding digital credit apps.

Privacy is defined as the ability of an individual to independently control access to and use of personal information. Its protection is not only a legal requirement, but a core element of autonomy, dignity, and trust in digital systems (Kosinski & Forrest, 2023). In the age of big data and AI, privacy is not just about the data that individuals actively disclose, but about how personal characteristics and assessments are derived algorithmically from existing data (Mai, 2016). While regulation exists, such as the Nigerian Data Protection Act (see below, Section 4.3), systematic data protection practices and legal loopholes remain in the Fintech sector (Ejechi, 2024).

One important factor of privacy is the consent to the collection, use, and sharing of data, for example, through privacy notices. Although the term consent is clearly defined in practice and explicit consent and authorization is often required by data protection law, for instance in Nigeria, there is often a lack of sufficient information about the type of data collected, the storage period, or whether the data are shared with possible third parties (CIPIT, 2021; Jemutai, 2025; Ejechi, 2024). While users are often willing to share personal information in exchange for monetary benefits, they still express concerns regarding data usage and access rights (Masinde et al., 2025).

Furthermore, a basic understanding of data protection rights is lacking among much of the public (Juma & Faturoti, 2025). A recent survey shows that many Kenyans do not understand what data they disclose and how they are used, for instance (Masinde et al.,

⁷ This risk story is based on a real case reported in March 2025. The article describes how a Kenyan credit app unlawfully accessed a user's phone contacts and falsely registered him as a guarantor for another person's loan. The affected individual received repeated threats and harassment. Kenya's Data Protection Authority (ODPC) investigated the incident and fined the company for violating consent requirements under the Data Protection Act (Abuya, 2025).

2025). Especially in rural areas, this low data literacy means many users are unaware of their rights and protections (Hove & Mafusire, 2025).

In sum, privacy and data protection are essential for individuals' agency. If data privacy ensures that individuals can control how their information is used, cybersecurity protects it from unauthorized access and exploitation (Jonker et al., 2025).

4.2.3. Risking Cybersecurity

To illustrate risks to cybersecurity, we tell the story of a businesswoman based in Ibadan.

Amara opens an app on her smartphone to check her digital savings. However, instead of the expected amount, the screen displays a zero balance. She grows concerned and begins checking her emails and social media accounts. Soon, it becomes apparent that she is not alone: thousands of users across Nigeria report similar incidents, their funds have disappeared overnight. Initially, the Fintech company blames external actors. Customers receive template emails promising updates. But days later, more disturbing details come to light. Insiders were involved.⁸

Amara's story underscores both cybersecurity risks and deeper ethical issues related to data misuse. Her experience is not an isolated case: One in ten Nigerians have already been affected by data leaks (Balogun, 2025). The result of such cybersecurity issues and repeated fraud cases, combined with weak complaint mechanisms, prompts a steady erosion of consumer trust (Balogun, 2025; Kolade, 2022).

As Buckley et al. (2019) explain, cyber risks have evolved into systemic threats that have the potential to destabilize entire financial ecosystems. Cybersecurity must therefore be understood not only as a technical protection, but as part of an ethical

⁸ This risk story draws on reporting about cybersecurity risks in Nigeria's Fintech sector (e.g. Olufemi, 2024). One of the most prominent cases involved the payment provider Flutterwave, where funds were fraudulently transferred to over 100 bank accounts, which led to 107 accounts across 27 banks being temporarily frozen (Akintaro, 2023).

infrastructure task that creates the conditions for informational autonomy and institutional accountability (Taddeo, 2016). Accountability means, in this context, that systems must be designed in such a way that people can be held responsible for misconduct or negligence (Floridi & Taddeo, 2016).

As a further point, the right to privacy explained in the previous section is ultimately disregarded in the case of cyberattacks or data leaks because of security issues. The Nigerian Data Protection Act explicitly refers to the rights of consumers, data security, and the secure handling of transactions (Kolade, 2022; Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2023).

4.2.4. Risking Control

Beyond technical vulnerabilities of cybersecurity, concerns also arise about who controls the structures that Fintech depends on. In this vein, the following fictional story of Nairobi-based artisan Azizi outlines the risk of outside control.

Azizi applies for a digital microloan with a popular Fintech headquartered in the US. Despite a perfect repayment history on previous digital loans, he is inexplicably denied the loan. This decision was made by the Fintech's AI-based credit scoring algorithm, which was trained on Western data. The model did not account for cultural differences and misinterpreted Azizi's local lifestyle patterns as unsuitable for the loan. When he tried to appeal the decision, there were no legal means available as the Fintech operated outside the reach of local users and regulators.⁹

To further illustrate this risk's relevance for Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda, *Figure 9* reworks the market overview from *Figure 8* to highlight the extent of non-African influence. Especially in payments and money transfer, the majority of companies are

⁹ This risk story is loosely inspired by reporting in Alliance for Financial Inclusion (2023) and Birhane (2023). However, since AI for African Fintech applications, such as credit scoring, is still being implemented, the consequences are not yet fully graspable.

either headquartered outside of Africa (shaded red in the figure), are subsidiaries of non-African providers (shaded green), or have a large proportion of non-African investors, often coming from the US or China (shaded blue). We see that especially Fintech giants such as Tala, Branch, and Flutterwave, which provide critical services and have large numbers of users, are based in the US.

Figure 9: Overview of Relevant Fintech Providers in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda, Categorized by Type of Non-African Influence. (Figure created by the authors. Companies shaded in red are headquartered outside of Africa; companies shaded in green have a non-African parent company; companies shaded in blue have a major share of non-African investors.)

Country	Digital Lending & Credit	Digital Payments & Transfer
Kenya		
Nigeria		
Rwanda		

Generally, AI tools are shaped by Western contexts and reflect the cultural norms and perspectives of their developers (Abbas, 2025). For many traditional Fintech companies, Western expectations that creditworthiness is “linked not only to wealth, but one’s character and trustworthiness” (Smith, 2025, p.4) shapes loan criteria. However, these criteria might apply differently to users in informal economies, such as street

vendors and artisans who typically rely on mobile money platforms. For example, statistics show that over 80% of Kenya's workforce works informally (Statista Research Department, 2025). While alternative data can provide local and contextual relevance, the methodological foundations of many credit scoring models usually remain anchored in globally established algorithmic frameworks, often developed in Western-dominated markets (Hassani, 2020; World Bank, 2024). Additionally, a reliance on alternative data introduces new risks and ethical challenges, as this report has shown in the previous sections. As a result, AI systems may continue to misclassify users, leading ultimately to unjust exclusion from critical financial services (Umeaduma & Adedapo, 2025).

This risk is exacerbated as many Fintech providers host their data and AI systems on cloud infrastructure situated in Europe or North America. Due to unequal data centre ownership in countries like Nigeria, Kenya, and Rwanda, the industry remains largely reliant on non-African infrastructure for core processing and storage (Goko, 2025; South African Reserve Bank, 2025). This leads to a loss of control over what happens with user data and may limit national sovereignty over critical digital assets (Howcroft, 2024; Mustapha, 2025; Venske, 2023).

Additionally, relying on globally dominant infrastructure providers can expose local financial systems to service disruptions of payment systems, geopolitical sanctions, and leaves data vulnerable to interception and misuse (South African Reserve Bank, 2025). In geopolitical tensions such as the US-China rivalry, Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda may risk reduced agency by becoming data-dependent on external stakeholders who control much of their Fintech infrastructure (Fambo, 2024)

Furthermore, when user data are stored outside national borders, they can become subject to the laws and surveillance practices of foreign jurisdictions. This allows foreign authorities and third parties to access African users' data without their knowledge or consent, undermining national data protection and weakening consumer rights (South African Reserve Bank, 2025). Settling disputes then becomes legally complex, often falling under foreign jurisdictions that may not recognize the standards of African privacy

rights. In the event of a breach where liability is unclear, consumers may face limited legal redress or slow, inaccessible remedies (South African Reserve Bank, 2025).

4.3. The Regulatory and Policy Context

In response to these risks, governments in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda propose and adopt various regulations and policies. *Table 3* shows an overview of this landscape, which is described in more detail in this section, as it relates to Fintech-specific policy, AI governance, and data protection regulation.

Table 3: Overview of Regulations and Policy Relevant to the Risks of Fintech.

Country	Fintech	Artificial Intelligence	Data protection
Kenya	No specific strategy, a fragmented and complex landscape with various statutes	<i>National Artificial Intelligence Strategy 2025-2030, 2025</i>	<i>Data Protection Act, 2019</i>
Nigeria	<i>National Fintech Strategy, 2022</i>	<i>National Artificial Intelligence Strategy (NAIS), 2024</i>	<i>Nigeria Data Protection Act, 2023</i>
Rwanda	<i>National Fintech Strategy (2024–2029), 2024</i>	<i>National AI Policy, 2023</i>	<i>Data Protection Law (n°058/2021), 2021</i>

4.3.1. Fintech Regulation and Policy in Comparison

Kenya, Nigeria and Rwanda have each taken regulatory approaches to governing Fintech, with differences in institutional maturity and strategic focus.

Kenya's Fintech sector is regulated through various statutes, including the Banking Act, Microfinance Act, National Payment Systems Act, Consumer Protection Act, and Kenya Information and Communications Act (Githu, 2023; Ndolo et al., 2025; Odongo, 2025). Oversight is shared among multiple regulatory bodies, such as the Central Bank of Kenya, the Communications Authority of Kenya, the Insurance Regulatory Authority, and the Sacco Societies Regulatory Authority (Githu, 2023; Ndolo et al., 2025). While recent measures, such as the proposed 2025 Virtual Asset Service Providers Bill, further address the regulation of emerging Fintech, the regulatory landscape remains fragmented and complex, posing challenges for coherence and implementation (Githu, 2023; Olendo, 2025).

Nigeria and Rwanda have adopted more specified, strategy-driven approaches. In Nigeria, the main regulatory body for Fintech is the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) (Aladejubelo et al., 2024, 18; Egemonye et al., 2025). Together with the National Financial Inclusion Steering Committee (2022b), it has launched the first National Fintech Strategy with a phased implementation approach roadmap and a special focus on financial inclusion. While the sector is already governed through many regulations and statutes, similar to Kenya, the Fintech Strategy aims to streamline this landscape through the design and implementation of a more coherent policy and regulation landscape, including the large-scale licensing of Fintech players.

Similarly, the Republic of Rwanda launched its first dedicated National Fintech Strategy in 2024, outlining a five-year roadmap (2024–2029) for sectoral development. It was spearheaded by the Ministry of ICT and Innovation and is further described in *Figure 10* (Gacuruzwa, 2025; Republic of Rwanda, 2024).

Figure 10: Rwanda’s Current Fintech Strategy on a Page. (Taken from “Shaping the future of Fintech in Rwanda: Fintech Strategy (2024–2029)” (Republic of Rwanda, 2024, p. 8).)

Despite these public Fintech policies, scholars note that challenges remain, such as the lack of strict enforcement and regulatory uncertainty linked to frequent changes and overlapping mandates (Aladejubelo et al., 2024; Onyegbula et al., 2023).

4.3.2. AI Regulation in Comparison

As of 2025, Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda have not enacted concrete, enforceable AI legislation. However, each country has introduced strategic frameworks to guide the responsible development and deployment of AI technologies.

Kenya’s Ministry of Information, Communications & The Digital Economy (2025) launched its National AI Strategy 2025–2030 in March 2025. This strategy is the most extensive of the three and adopts a phased implementation approach. It starts with

investments in policy, infrastructure, and capacity building, followed by developing a national AI policy, setting up AI research and innovation hubs, launching pilot projects, and establishing a monitoring and evaluation framework. Complementing this, the Kenya Bureau of Standards (KEBS) published a Draft Artificial Intelligence Code of Practice in 2024 with recommendations for organizations on the responsible development, provision, and use of AI (Kenya Bureau of Standards, 2024).

In Nigeria, the Federal Ministry of Communication, Innovation and Digital Economy (2024) released the draft *National Artificial Intelligence Strategy (NAIS)* in August 2024 (Shin & Lee, 2025). It outlines ambitions to establish a dedicated AI Governance Regulatory Body as well as an AI Ethics Expert Group, which will “define the ethical principles that align with critical Nigerian values” (Federal Ministry of Communication, Innovation and Digital Economy, 2024, pp. 40–42).

Rwanda, comparatively, was an early mover, having gained Cabinet approval for its National AI Policy in April 2023 (Magoro, 2023; Ministry of ICT and Innovation, 2022). The policy explicitly identifies banking and digital payments as priority sectors, and its implementation is supported by institutional mechanisms such as a national AI office and the Rwanda Utilities Regulatory Authority (Kaaruu, 2024; Kwarkye, 2025; Ministry of ICT and Innovation, 2022).

Despite these promising strategies, the effectiveness of AI policy across all three countries remains constrained not just by the non-binding nature of ethical guidelines but also by broader systemic challenges, including insufficient local infrastructure and the limited capacity to hold multinational technology companies accountable for breaches (Amaechi, 2025; Kwarkye, 2025).

4.3.3. Data Protection Regulation in Comparison

Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda are among the 46 out of 54 African countries that currently have legal regulations on data protection (Akintolu, 2025). These regulations were partly influenced by the so-called Brussels Effect, which has prompted many countries

worldwide, including those in Africa, to incorporate aspects of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) into their legal frameworks (Boshe & Caride, 2024).

In response to the shortcomings of the previous regulatory framework, the Nigerian Data Protection Act was signed into law in 2023, establishing the Nigeria Data Protection Commission (NDPC) as an independent authority (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2023; Akintolu, 2025). The main objectives of the law are to establish a solid regulatory authority, to provide legal mechanisms in the event of violations, and to sustainably strengthen the trust of citizens and companies in Nigeria's digital economy (DLA Piper, 2025a). In addition, the law requires data controllers to carry out a risk assessment and implement proportionate safeguards (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2023).

Kenya's data protection regulation journey started earlier. The Kenyan Data Protection Act came into force in 2019, making Kenya one of the first African countries to have a comprehensive data protection law. An independent supervisory authority, the Office of the Data Protection Commissioner (ODPC), monitors compliance and enforcement of the regulation (Republic of Kenya, 2019; Amnesty International Kenya, 2025; DLA Piper, 2025b). Moreover, the ODPC (2024) has issued sector-specific guidance notes for the health, education, digital credit providers, and communications sectors, aimed at helping institutions understand and comply with their obligations under the Data Protection Act (ODPC, 2024). This Act explicitly requires setting up data protection impact assessments (Republic of Kenya, 2019).

Promulgated in October 2021, Law No. 058/2021 on the Protection of Personal Data and Privacy serves as the cornerstone of modern data protection rights in Rwanda. Its enforcement is overseen by the National Cyber Security Authority (Rwanda Information and Society Authority, n.d.). In addition, in May 2025, Rwanda adopted a National Data Sharing Policy to regulate the secure data exchange between government agencies (Republic of Rwanda, 2025). Both policies require a privacy impact assessment and stress its necessity for safe data sharing (Republic of Rwanda, 2025).

Nonetheless, concerns remain that regulators often struggle to force powerful international companies to comply with regulations, and mean there is a gap between legislation and actual accountability (Akintolu, 2025).

4.4. Concluding Remarks: Risk

This section has explored Fintech in the context of Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda with a central focus on risks. We have shown how systems intended to promote financial inclusion can simultaneously reproduce or even exacerbate the existing structural inequities they promise to abolish. Thus while Fintech is often heralded as a catalyst for inclusion by offering new ways to access credit and make payments, the risks we examined underscore that this promise is highly contingent on the conditions of its implementation. From universalised credit requirements and biased algorithms to harassing methods and weak data protection, our findings highlight a recurring theme: Although we presented them in different forms, many of these risks are interlinked. They reveal a broader story of systems that often privilege the already privileged while marginalizing the marginalized.

A concept that has not been explicitly mentioned in earlier sections but emerges as a central thread uniting the risks discussed here is exploitation. As Fintech systems are not created in a vacuum, they build on unequal infrastructures, which are governed by opaque algorithms, and feed business models that often extract value from already marginalized communities. This is especially concerning when regulation does not sufficiently protect users and opting out is not a real choice, as access to credit, business opportunities, and entire livelihoods depend on engaging with these platforms. Consent becomes blurred when basic financial participation requires surrendering control over one's data or navigating opaque risk scoring systems.

To mitigate these risks, emerging Fintech hubs such as Rwanda should focus on redistributing power and fostering fairer, more resilient systems. To achieve this, the following strategic actions can be considered: First, stronger licensing and regulatory enforcement for digital lenders is crucial in order to curb predatory practices, increase

accountability, and ensure that financial services operate with transparency and fairness (AfricaNenda Foundation, 2024). In addition, regulatory approaches should require strong impact assessments, as exemplified by Kenya's and Rwanda's data protection laws. But industry self-regulation can go further in taking responsibility from within, and critically examine fairness and inclusiveness in their technologies, centre humans in their designs from the start, adopt ethical standards, and invest in bias audits (Sam-Abugu et al., 2025; Shittu et al., 2024). Further, reducing reliance on outside infrastructure and companies requires targeted investment in local data infrastructure and innovation ecosystems (Benamara, 2025). Embedding financial and data literacy education and spreading public awareness through campaigns, especially in rural areas, can additionally empower users to navigate these systems more safely, understand their rights, and hold providers accountable. It is especially critical to engage marginalized and vulnerable groups in decision-making and design, as they should be active co-creators rather than passive users.

Ultimately, Fintech's potential lies not just in innovation, but in ethical and inclusive design. To ensure that inclusion does not become the new mode of exclusion, both technological development and policy must be rooted in social responsibility.

5. Opportunities

This section examines how Rwanda can encourage ethical AI growth in its fintech industry, by focusing on opportunities that are distinct to Rwanda's unique regulatory, infrastructural, and cultural landscape. We use research, comparisons with other countries (especially Kenya and Nigeria), and discussions during the data clinic with our partner, the Certa Foundation, to identify two main types of problems: those related to the government and the law, and those related to social issues. This section connects these problems to potential opportunities to promote fairness, responsibility, and participation.

The section outlines strategic interventions ranging from regulatory reforms to innovative, user-centred technology solutions. Problems include unethical debt recovery

practices, insufficient data governance, and lack of connectivity. Potential opportunities include setting up third-party auditing or evaluation systems, tax rebates, or automated micro-insurance payouts. These kinds of opportunities offer a way to create AI-enhanced finance services that are not only technically sound but also responsive to societies.

5.1. Defining Opportunity

We define opportunities as ethical and practical openings to improve the use of Fintech in African ecosystems with a focus on fairness, transparency, and accountability. Instead of immediately proposing solutions, we began by analysing existing challenges within the sector. We believe that a clear understanding of the challenges provides a more grounded basis for identifying relevant and realistic opportunities.

To identify these challenges, we draw on the previous sections as well as on selected legal and ethical standpoints. Through this process, we categorize the challenges into two main groups: governmental challenges and social challenges. Governmental challenges refer to structural and institutional barriers that hinder the effective regulation and ethical deployment of AI technologies in Fintech. These challenges often relate to policy design, and the presence or absence of formal legal frameworks. Social challenges, in contrast, arise from interactions between technology and the lived realities of individuals and communities. They involve the ways in which social, cultural, and economic conditions affect people's ability to access, trust, and benefit from AI-driven financial services.

From these categories of challenges, two opportunity groups arose. Governmental opportunities focus on improving regulation and oversight. Social opportunities emphasize user-centred approaches. For example, these may include setting up public auditing mechanisms or developing inclusive app designs to support users with low digital literacy. This classification provides the structure for the following sections, where we present and discuss specific challenges and the opportunities that emerge from them.

5.2. Challenges from a Legal Standpoint

5.2.1. Challenges in Debt Collection Laws and Enforcement

Although consumer protection regulation exists in Rwanda, it has enforcement gaps as identified above in the risks section of this report. There is no oversight of malpractice in debt collection and no accountability for harassment during debt collection (Jalal-Eddeen, 2024).

In the Nigerian context, the FCCPC (Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission) has clear guidelines for curbing unethical debt recovery practices. Enforcement is also prioritized. In Kenya, the Digital Credit Providers Regulation restricts harassment and mandates debt recovery from lenders by the lending Fintech companies. The OPDC (Office of the Data Protection Commissioner) heavily enforces fines and sanctions on violators (Abba, 2021). In Rwanda, in contrast, no laws directly mandate or regulate debt collection practices in the consumer protection regulations issued by the National Bank of Rwanda. Nor does Rwanda enforce its laws as strictly as the other two countries in question (Animhiaga, 2025).

An increasing number of illegal incidents have been reported relating to debt collection. The debtor's call log information and stored contact information was widely used to reach family members, neighbours, close relatives, and friends to increase social pressure on them by conveying them threatening messages and warnings to ensure debt collection, for instance through continuous harassment (Animhiaga, 2025).

5.2.2. Opportunities for Debt Collection Laws and Enforcement

Privacy Protection Laws

Since there are relatively weak laws protecting the consumer and weak enforcement of such laws, changes to the current regulations could be proposed, with stricter policy mandates around debt collection practices and to ensure consumer data is not used to create social pressure or harass the consumer or his associates. There is an opportunity for more privacy protection laws from the government, especially to account

for loopholes in national AI policy and the consumer protection regulations issued by the National Bank of Rwanda. *Figure 11* sketches out such an opportunity regarding who would be the actor and the beneficiaries, as well as touching on issues of feasibility, implementation, and a potential mechanism (see also Amaechi, 2025).

Figure 11: Evaluation Schematic for the Opportunity of More Privacy Protection Laws.

Regulatory Bodies

The AI Act of Rwanda mentions the creation of a ROAI (Responsible Office for Artificial Intelligence). The problem, however, lies not simply in ensuring the use of AI in a fair, transparent, and legitimate way; there are also cases of harassment during debt collection. In recent years we have seen task forces being formed in the developing world to work on specific tasks and produce results quickly. The Rwandan government could create a task force with the mandate to receive complaints and address harassment related to debt collection separately. It would enforce relevant data protection laws and AI regulatory laws in alignment with the national AI policy and the consumer protection regulations issued by the National Bank of Rwanda (see also Donovan & Park, 2022). This opportunity might both create jobs and also contribute to a healthy, constructive and competitive business environment for all lending startups in the Fintech space (Sommer et al., 2025). *Figure 12* schematises this opportunity, its actors, beneficiaries, feasibility, implementation, and potential mechanism.

Figure 12: Evaluation Schematic for the Opportunity of Creating Regulatory Bodies, Agencies and Departments.

5.2.3. Challenges in AI Ethics and Data Governance

As reported above, a potential risk in the use of AI in Fintech across Rwanda is that ethical guidelines are advisory and not binding. Ethical AI development is encouraged, but Rwanda's "Guidelines on the Ethical Development and Implementation of AI" are non-mandatory and not backed by strong legal enforcement (see Ministry of ICT and Innovation, 2022). This is perhaps a classic case of the Collingridge dilemma, where legislators and think tanks are reluctant to step in with strict laws due to a fear that they could potentially stall growth in a sector. However, this becomes a catch-22-situation where if you wait too long to bring in strong laws to protect consumers or society, the situation might fall massively out of control (for Nigeria, see Federal Ministry of Communication, 2024).

Moreover, data governance standards are vague. The national AI policy talks about developing "frameworks and protocols for data sharing" but lacks clear, enforceable provisions on data ownership, consent mechanisms, and accountability in cases of data misuse. Additionally, data collection and storage often operate outside of the jurisdiction of the government of Rwanda. Most of the Fintech Platforms in Rwanda use data collection and processing overseas, as seen in Figure 9 in Section 4.

The Rwandan Law for Governance of Data (Law No. 058/2021) regulates that a data breach is to be reported within 48 hours of its inception and a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is to be formulated. The relevant Data protection officers (DPO) are

to be hired in accordance. Nigeria and Kenya both have Data Protection acts that operate in a similar fashion. The Nigeria Data Protection Act (2023) lays huge emphasis on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) in cases of data breaches. It mandates a system of privacy by design and is explicit on automated decisions and profiling, which should be aligned with the EU GDPR (Kenya Data Protection Act, 2019; Nigeria Data Protection Act, 2023). The Kenyan Data Protection Act (2019) focuses on automated processing and specially on the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). Consent to data gathering is a key feature here.

5.2.4. Opportunities for AI Ethics, Data Governance and Data Monitoring Accreditation System

Challenges linked to weak governance can be addressed through approach of forming third-party audit companies that would evaluate Fintechs and their activities for ethical behaviour and fair and transparent use of AI, as well as compliance with the Data protection and AI regulatory law for Rwanda. This could be mandated voluntarily by Fintech companies or designated by the authorities. An audit report consisting of behavioural aspects could not only serve consumers, but also keep the authorities informed about discrepancies. Furthermore, for Fintechs themselves, it could be a useful marketing tool to indicate they adhere to ethical guidelines (Hove, & Mafusire, 2025).

This could potentially be implemented through an accreditation system that rates Fintech companies by their ethical norms and use of AI in a fair and transparent approach towards their lenders. The Stiftung Warentest in Germany is an example of such an accreditation system for a range of sectors. Having a high accreditation score could become a marketing/advertisement tool for Fintechs and can also become a unique selling point (USP) for their future customers. *Figure 13* below schematises this opportunity, its actors, beneficiaries, feasibility, implementation, and potential mechanism.

Figure 13: Evaluation Schematic for the Opportunity of an Accreditation System for Privacy Protection.

Tax Rebates

An environment of checks and balances could be created by offering tax concessions are offered to Fintech companies that adhere to engage with and positively respond to audit conclusions. Audits of fairness and transparency would be carried out by third-party audit companies or a governmental regulatory board/body. This option creates an environment where strict laws can be avoided if necessary and, additionally, promotes healthy competition between Fintech companies. Of course, it also entails fiscal challenges since taxes are a huge revenue stream of any government. Well balanced, it could allow an environment that promotes economic activities and also cover grounds for self-imposed checks and balances. *Figure 14* below schematises this opportunity, its actors, beneficiaries, feasibility, implementation, and potential mechanism.

Figure 14: Evaluation Schematic for the Opportunity of Creating Tax Rebates.

Nationalised Fintech Data Companies

One very radical opportunity would be to create nationalized companies for data gathering and ownership in the Fintech sector. This would largely become a possibility if the government of Rwanda felt that data monitoring and ownership were a matter of utmost importance and of national security. Since most Fintech data are mined, stored, and accessed abroad, this countermeasure would create ownership of the data for the government of Rwanda. *Figure 15* below schematises this opportunity, its actors, beneficiaries, feasibility, implementation, and potential mechanism.

Figure 15: Evaluation Schematic for the Opportunity of the Formation of Separate Nationalized Companies for Data Gathering and Ownership.

5.3. Challenges and Opportunities from Social and Ethical Aspects

This section addresses key social and ethical challenges that hinder inclusive Fintech development in Africa, including limited access and control over financial services, discrimination, low adoption rates of Fintech applications, and barriers to supporting agricultural livelihoods. By analysing these issues—ranging from functionality gaps to societal inequalities—we aim to identify innovative, responsible, and context-sensitive opportunities for ethical digital finance solutions.

5.3.1. Unpaid Care Work and Financial Exclusion of Rural Women

Challenge

Caregiving duties including childcare and elder care support are mostly performed by women in Rwanda's rural communities. Despite being necessary, this labour is nonetheless unpaid and unseen from an economic standpoint. Because of this, women who provide full-time care frequently may not have access to financial assistance, economic independence, or formal system acknowledgment. This results in a vicious cycle of reliance and exclusion from advancements in digital banking. Gender-based inequity is maintained because traditional financial instruments and credit-scoring systems do not recognize the economic worth of providing care (IPAR & IDRC, 2022; Lalani et al., 2025).

Opportunity: Time-Banking Platform for Rural Caregivers

Setting up a computerized time-banking (Fintech) platform that lets rural caregivers keep track of their hours of care and trade them for “time credits” that can be used later is one possible solution. Caregivers could later use these credits for things such as food packages, medical consultations, school supplies, or small loans. Those with limited digital skills could access the platform via text messaging, for example, or through an app that is made just for them. Cooperatives, village elders, or community health workers would validate the hours worked and services used at the local level. This program has the potential to give women more influence by recognizing caregiving as work that is important for the economy. It would bring people together in the community, and include women in financial institutions through a different, more open way of exchanging value (George, 2024; Manta & Palazzo, 2024).

5.3.2. Climate Risk and Smallholder Farmers

Challenge

Climate change is making smallholder farmers in Rwanda more vulnerable because it causes irregular rainfall, long droughts, and crop failures. However, difficult claims processes, long wait times for payouts, and expensive administrative costs mean that

traditional agricultural insurance policies frequently do not adequately protect these farmers. After a climatic shock, many families become stuck in poverty as they wait for compensation, putting their long-term resilience and food security at risk. As a result, insurance is not very common, even though it can lower risk (Dale 2021).

Opportunity: Parametric Micro-Insurance via Smart Contracts

A parametric micro-insurance model based on smart contracts is a scalable and effective way to solve problems. This technology would do away with the necessity for handwritten claims by automatically sending payments to farmers based on set meteorological conditions, such the amount of rain or vegetation indices from satellites. Using smart contracts on the blockchain makes sure that things are clear, work well, and save money. The service could be offered via mobile money services in rural locations. Such an expansion of Fintech might not only help farmers continue working, but also build faith in insurance systems by making sure that smallholder farmers get fair and timely payments after climatic disasters. It could also help with the bigger goals of making nutrition more secure and making the environment more resilient (Etherisc, 2024).

5.3.3. Low Literacy

Challenge

Rwanda has quickly adopted mobile technology, but certain individuals—especially women, the elderly, and those living in rural areas—have difficulty using digital financial services due to having low literacy or not knowing how to use text-based interfaces. Most Fintech solutions need users to be able to read and write and know how to use a smartphone, which makes it hard for those who usually communicate verbally to use them. This creates a digital gap, where people who are already disadvantaged cannot fully participate in or benefit from the growing financial ecosystem (Mumporeze & Prieler, 2017).

Opportunity: Voice-Enabled Fintech Services for Low-Literacy Users

An inclusive approach could comprise the implementation of voice-enabled banking services via Interactive Voice Response (IVR), chatbots in indigenous languages such as Kinyarwanda, and AI-driven speech-to-text systems. Users would dial a local number, inquire about financial matters vocally, and obtain clear responses either verbally or by SMS. Large Language Models (LLMs) trained on localized data could improve personalization and understanding. These services would be available through basic mobile phones. This initiative would foster digital inclusion by rendering financial services accessible to low-literacy individuals and enhances trust through culturally tailored interactions (Kogen and Smith 2016).

5.3.4. Digital Financial Inclusion

Challenge: Connectivity Barriers

In many Rwandan rural communities, poor internet and mobile network connectivity continue to be major obstacles to financial inclusion. People in areas with poor connectivity continue to rely on cash since digital transactions are unstable, even with the widespread availability of mobile money services. Thus, a significant portion of the population is unable to access secure, real-time financial services due to a lack of infrastructure for digital payments (Grzybowski et al., 2023).

Opportunity: Offline-Capable Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC)

A Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) that may be used without an internet connection could help bridge this digital gap. Token-based CBDC transactions do not need to be linked to the internet or a network to work. People can buy things in places that are not connected to the internet, such stores, markets, or hospitals. When the connection is made, the transaction data is synchronised. Implementing such a currency could encourage fair access to money and make people less reliant on cash (Kim and Yoon, 2025).

6. Conclusions

As African countries like Rwanda, Kenya, and Nigeria continue their digital and financial transformations, the ethical deployment of AI-driven Fintech solutions becomes both a necessity and an opportunity. While digital lending offers significant potential to expand financial inclusion, it also presents serious ethical and governance challenges.

Following the “data journey” allowed us to make visible the human decisions and institutional structures that shape algorithmic credit systems. Addressing these requires a deliberate and systemic approach to transparency, accountability, and equity—one that recognizes the socio-technical complexity of algorithmic systems and places the interests of vulnerable users at the centre of innovation and reform.

We further addressed some emerging risks associated with Fintech developments in Kenya, Nigeria, and Rwanda. Despite a growing discourse on inclusion in Fintech, issues such as algorithmic fairness, privacy violations, cybersecurity vulnerabilities, and external dependencies remain underrepresented. To shed light on this imbalance, this report included a risk-oriented analysis of user-side Fintech, using policy literature, fictionalized risk stories, and selected market data to highlight concrete challenges. Findings indicate that while digital financial technologies are widely praised for enhancing financial inclusion, the structural risks they entail, particularly in regions with limited regulatory frameworks and infrastructural disparities, are often neglected. Fintech may entrench structural inequalities through opaque algorithmic decision-making, exploitative data practices, and outside control of infrastructures.

This report has shown that responsible innovation cannot be achieved through technology alone—it must be grounded in individual countries’ social realities, institutional capacities, and legal frameworks. From weak enforcement of debt collection laws to the exclusion of rural women and smallholder farmers from digital finance, the challenges are deeply rooted in both structural governance and everyday lived experiences. However, these challenges also open the door to context-sensitive opportunities: community-based time-banking, voice-enabled financial tools, parametric insurance, ethical audit systems, and inclusive data governance mechanisms. By

aligning AI innovation with fairness, accountability, and user-centric design, responsible Fintech development in Africa should prioritize inclusion and human dignity while fostering economic resilience. The analysis outlined in this report offers actionable steps for policymakers, Fintech companies, and civil society to collectively build a more just and effective financial future.

We stress that a just and inclusive Fintech future requires more than technical innovation: It demands political accountability, social equity, and user agency. While the report focused on selected risks and opportunities, it was limited by the absence of direct engagement with affected communities. Future research needs to include empirical fieldwork and engagement with a wide variety of stakeholders, further examine regulatory enforcement, and explore how current risks can be translated into concrete opportunities. Additionally, broader dimensions of exploitation that fall outside the scope of this analysis deserve closer attention. For example, assessing the long-term sustainability issues of AI-enabled Fintech, the workforce exploitation behind the industry, and the outflow of value from local economies to global tech corporations. Addressing these interconnected issues will be essential to fully assess the ethical and socio-economic consequences of Fintech expansion.

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Appendix

Table 4: Data Gathering Exploratory Analysis

Nombre del alumno	Type	Data + Source				Country	Link	Motivation	Relevance
		Data	Data Categories	Source	Sources Categories				
Zowisee, ACCESS	Fintech - Financial Services	Soil info, market info, yield forecasts, agency data, farmer KYC, mobile phones, alternative data, anonymized credit bureau data, community social underwriting Stakeholder:	market specific data (soil, market, yield, forecasts) - mobile phone data - Traditional financial data - identity verification	high-frequency and recent farmer attributes; collection loan requirement data (farm size, crop yield, harvest, crop types, historic sales, agricultural activity), KYC, mobile data	app - user - device - credit bureau / black lists, ID verifier	Nigeria	https://www.zowisee.com/alternative.html#329 https://mobsum.com/zowisee/the-future-of-alternative-credit-scoring-for-digital-banks-749336c66d	a	We support and deploy our technologies across the continent and ground operations in Nigeria, Kenya, and Tanzania, enabling partner organizations across different geographies to deploy our solutions.
Social Lender	Fintech - Financial Services	Friends, family, connections on Social Lender; referees/guarantors; user dashboard usability Stakeholder:	Social media data - Existing Client data - App connections - Identity verification	Social reputation data via friends/references/guarantors; confirmation of loan request; bank debit verification from guarantors; Social media	app - user - natural persons- social media apps	Nigeria, Kenya, Tanzania	bincom.net/Social Lender		Social Lender is designed to bridge the gap of immediate access for people with limited access to formal financial services.
Lendag / Oraculi / Adjutor	Scoretech / Financial Software	Data from borrower (address, place of work, etc.) - Device data (location, telemetric data via GSM) - Lender ecosystem (e.g. Karma, prior loans) - External sources (credit bureau, blacklists) - Analytics (Lendag ML engine, partners like Periculus) - Borrower's bank account statements Stakeholder:	Existing client data - Mobile phone data - Digital financial data - Traditional financial data	Data input by borrower during loan application - Data collected from device after user grants permission to SDK-enabled app - Data and analyzed by backend after encryption - User demographic attributes listed explicitly (age, employment status, income, BVN, education, residence, etc.) -	user - device - app - credit bureau (black lists) - Fintech ecosystem - Borrowers bank	Nigeria	https://lendag.freshdesk.com/support/solutions/articles/4400244578-what-is-decision-data https://lendag.freshdesk.com/support/solutions/articles/4400276620-evaluate-customer-creditworthiness-using-adjutor-oraculi-adjutor-scoring https://docs.adjutor.io/adjutor-api-endpoints/oraculi-mobile-sdk-beta/the-oraculi-sdk-data-journey		We simplify launching your own loan business by transforming regulatory and capital challenges into opportunities. Our lending technology and resources streamline your lending process, making it easier for you to start! 7000+ lenders We're helping lenders across the world value their loan business.
Rubyx	Scoretech / Financial Software	Existing client data, customer financial behavior, CRM records, product holdings, data warehouse inputs (shared or proprietary) Stakeholder:	Existing Client data - Behavior within app - Digital financial data, Other data	Customer interactions and profile data via CRM, recovery and performance metrics, tailored segment listings from data warehouse	app - fintech ecosystem	Rwanda	https://www.rubyx.io/solutions/		With the accelerated digital transformation and rise of digital platforms, the promise of embedded lending and API led product growth, today we need to reach as many entrepreneurs as possible by facilitating partnerships between digital platforms and financial institutions. Together, we're going to make a big difference. Motivation: https://www.rubyx.io/good-data-empigs-begins-with-good-questions/
Tala	Fintech - Financial Services	Android device data (e.g. device type, OS, year, installed apps) - Behavioral app interaction data - Equipment behavior - Historic user data Stakeholder:	Mobile phone data - Behavior within app - Digital financial data	Permission-based data collection via Android OS - Monitoring app user behavior - Recording loan repayment behavior over time	device - app	Kenya	https://tala.co/~/data-etl-ics/		Back in 2011, Tala saw a challenge and an opportunity: billions of people around the world lacked access to traditional financial services, not because they didn't need them, but because the existing systems weren't built to include them. Driven by necessity, Tala set out to change that. the largest non-bank lender in Kenya and the top digital lending app across the current markets.